

CODECHECK certificate 2025-018

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15630442>

Item	Value
Title	Scalable control synthesis for stochastic systems via structural IMPDP abstractions
Authors	Frederik Baymler Mathiesen (0000-0002-2243-0445) Sofie Haesaert (0000-0003-4749-4688) and Luca Laurenti (0000-0003-1190-6097)
Publication	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.11803
Publication repository	https://doi.org/10.4121/2c221b54-a20b-4659-99d2-af4a9a114b60.v2
Codecheckers	Niket Agrawal (0000-0002-3208-3440)
Date of check	2025-05-28
Summary	Tables 2, 3, and 4, as well as Figures 4 and 5 from the manuscript, were successfully reproduced by following the instructions provided in the README file. Instructions were only available for reproducing these specific tables and figures. To avoid the lengthy execution time required to run the full experiments, the pre-computed results provided in the repository were used to generate the tables and figures, as recommended in the README.
Codecheck repository	https://github.com/codecheckers/certificate-2025-008

Table 1: CODECHECK summary

Summary

- Tables 2, 3, and 4, as well as Figures 4 and 5 from the manuscript, were successfully reproduced by following the instructions provided in the README file. The README file is at the root of the code repository. Instructions were only available for reproducing these specific tables and figures.
- As mentioned in the README, the experiments are computationally intensive, requiring at least 100 GB of RAM and 12 CPU cores, and can take several weeks to finish executing. To avoid the lengthy execution time required to run the full experiments, the pre-computed results provided in the repository were used to generate the tables and figures, as recommended in the README.

Output	Comment
table_2_computation_performance.csv	manuscript Table 2
table_3_satisfaction_probability.csv	manuscript Table 3
table_4_car_parking.csv	manuscript Table 4
plot_4_car_parking.pdf	manuscript Figure 4
plot_5_convergence_analysis.pdf	manuscript Figure 5

Table 2: Summary of output files generated

CODECHECKER notes

The authors have made available all the necessary code and data required to reproduce figures in the manuscript. These resources can be accessed in the 4TU.ResearchData repository: <https://data.4tu.nl/datasets/2c221b54-a20b-4659-99d2-af4a9a114b60/2>

Setup

The results (tables and figures) were reproduced on a Windows machine using Windows Subsystem for Linux with Ubuntu 24.04.2. As specified in the README, Docker was required to run experiments. Docker version 28.2.2 was installed and used for this purpose.

Used pre-computed results to generate figures and tables

To reproduce the plots and figures presented in the manuscript, the instructions provided in the README file of the linked code repository were followed. The README outlines the steps required to reproduce Tables 2, 3, and 4, as well as Figures 4 and 5. By adhering to these instructions, the specified tables and figures could be reproduced.

As mentioned in the README, the experiments are computationally intensive, requiring at least 100 GB of RAM and 12 CPU cores, and can take several weeks to finish executing. To avoid the lengthy execution time required to run the full experiments, the pre-computed results provided in the repository were used to generate the tables and figures, as recommended in the README. The README contains instructions and commands to avoid running full experiments and instead use pre-computed results to generate the figures and the tables.

Manifest Files

plot_4_car_parking.pdf

Comment: Figure 4 in the manuscript

plot_5_convergence_analysis.pdf

Comment: Figure 5 in the manuscript

table_2_computation_performance.csv

Comment: Table 2 in the manuscript

name	odimdp_abstraction_time	odimdp_certification_time	odimdp_prob_mem	imdp_abstraction_time	imdp_certification_time	imdp_prob_mem	impact_abstraction_time	impact_certification_time	impact_prob_mem
dubins_car_gp_dkl	13.81639105	19.56218538	352.154572	336.9399322	31.3330167	14265.75902	NaN	NaN	NaN
bas4d	0.022830748	0.236708123	2.897432	7.272964141	0.285433708	105.059676	17.564	0.318	96.04
linear_stochastically_switched	0.032828195	0.044778203	4.548652	3.391326286	0.037905204	41.030696	NaN	NaN	NaN
robot_2d_reachability	0.665322997	0.167951465	21.634552	12.65847498	0.129106395	88.037472	20.611	0.765	306.66262
hndm_cartpole	236.1539063	550.7467754	611.442908	42326.40032	3.751213305	1590.918472	NaN	NaN	NaN
linear6d	8.95941323	359.8865001	237.271508	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
linear7d	66.23140213	13903.53958	2329.968132	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
car_parking	0.149941417	0.145592169	19.246956	13.49703406	0.255441505	138.146144	19.57	0.846	304.9382
van_der_pol	1.657714189	0.257011654	45.514968	27.25482632	0.827186841	353.560384	113.235	3.233	1093.4004
robot_2d_reachavoid	14.25858628	7.641159639	547.205636	1136.720091	6.73937253	4143.789152	918.856	37.526	16387.981

table_3_satisfaction_probability.csv

Comment: Table 3 in the manuscript

name	odimd p_mean n_prob	odimd p_mean n_err	imdp_ mean_ prob	imdp_ mean_ error	imdp_ min_ prob_diff	imdp_ max_ prob_diff	imdp_ avg_ prob_diff	imdp_ avg_ prob_diff	impact_ mean_ prob	impact_ mean_ error	impact_ min_ prob_diff	impact_ max_ prob_diff	impact_ avg_ prob_diff
dubins _car_g p_dkl	0.3618 48828	0.3460 7029	0.2160 83367	0.5046 12218		0.8382 7025	0.1457 6546		NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
bas4d	0.2633 81581	0.7336 17397	0.0900 41462	0.9075 52167	0.0510 11266	0.2296 91275	0.1733 40119	0.1736 42755	0.8237 26594	0.0303 80088	0.1130 85452	0.0897 38826	
linear_ stochas tically_ switch ed	0.4114 42647	0.2828 47092	0.3658 12433	0.3604 85831	1.90E- 06	0.0978 90467	0.0456 30214		NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
robot_ 2d_rea chabilit y	0.8892 1788	0.1107 61883	0.8813 56428	0.1186 28474	0.0059 92187	0.0118 64023	0.0078 61452	0.8902 11169	0.1097 75737	0.0057 94382	0.0022 21171	0.0009 93289	
nndm_ cartpol e	0.0037 12224	0.7633 59494	5.24E- 09	0.7183 78116	-1.22E- 15	0.4100 79455	0.0037 12219		NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
linear6 d	0.9581 27812	0.0418 62759	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
linear7 d	0.9517 09252	0.0482 79721	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
car_pa rking	0.2687 03695	0.3885 28444	0.2127 38476	0.5315 16591	0.0040 28623	0.1428 0555	0.0559 65219	0.2130 61863	0.5182 68229	0.0040 20587	0.1421 5255	0.0556 41832	
van_de r_pol	0.0691 56797	0.3366 60231	0.0514 37907	0.4178 39056	3.82E- 110	0.0528 75211	0.0177 18889		NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
robot_ 2d_rea chavoi d	0.9799 66909	0.0199 11571	0.9791 33952	0.0207 58723	0.0004 52377	0.0026 82901	0.0008 32957	0.9797 02864	0.0201 92979	0.0001 05514	0.0018 37305	0.0002 64044	

table_4_car_parking.csv

Comment: Table 4 in the manuscript

num_regions	syscore_mem_mb	syscore_eps	odimdp_mem_mb	odimdp_eps
22500	7.203978	0.125402384	937.85606	0.006994719
10000	3.203178	0.156759118	279.50737	0.010655293
360000	115.211178	0.006014842	59499.08377	0.001416572
90000	28.806378	0.028783168	7459.019402	0.002838414
2500	0.802378	0.264996946	35.54817963	0.020350222

Acknowledgements

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Citing this document

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About CODECHECK

This certificate confirms that the codecheckers could independently reproduce the results of a computational analysis given the data and code from a third party. A CODECHECK does not check whether the original computation analysis is correct. However, as all materials required for the reproduction are freely available by following the links in this document, the reader can then study for themselves the code and data.